

Online repository

On the Interaction between Software Engineers and Data Scientists when Building Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

This online repository contains the transcriptions of all the interviews we conducted during our study. In the following, we outline the material.

Content

Filename	Description
DS1_Interview.pdf	Transcription of the interview with Data Scientist 1
DS2_Interview.pdf	Transcription of the interview with Data Scientist 2
SE1_Interview.pdf	Transcription of the interview with Software Engineer 1
SE2_Interview.pdf	Transcription of the interview with Software Engineer 2